

Distal sedimentation from large-volume silicic eruptions in a regression-dominated marine environment

A flight of Last Glacial river terraces preserved in the Rangitikei Valley taken from Taraketi Road

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Table of Contents

Introduction	3
Whanganui Basin.....	6
Taupō Volcanic Zone.....	8
DAY 1	12
STOP 1 – Waitapu Stream.....	12
Rātā Marae Lunch.....	16
STOP 2 – Otara Bridge	16
STOP 3 – Ruahine Road	19
Makoura Lodge Accomodation	22
DAY 2	23
STOP 4 – Table Flat Road	23
STOP 5 – Oroua Valley Lookout	24
STOP 6 – Finnis Road	26
Raumai Reserve Lunch	28
STOP 7 – Broadlands Station	28
STOP 8 – Te Ahu a Turanga	30
Return to Palmerston North	33
References.....	34
Appendix A – Cyclothem Motifs	43
Appendix B – Whanganui Basin Chronology	44
Appendix C – Waitapu Shell Conglomerate Fossils.....	45
Appendix D – Waitapu Shell Conglomerate Fossil List	46

Introduction

Welcome to our field trip through the Plio-Pleistocene Whanganui Basin (WB) in the Manawatū-Whanganui Region of the lower North Island, Aotearoa New Zealand (Fig. 1). The trips overarching theme is the influence of large-volume silicic volcanism on sedimentation within a dominantly shallow-marine sedimentary basin. More specifically, we will be exploring primary and reworked deposits from the Taupō Volcanic Zone (TVZ) in the central North Island of Aotearoa New Zealand, which form key marker horizons within the WB sedimentary succession, underpinning the basins chronostratigraphic framework and facilitating field mapping and regional correlation.

The WB contains one of the most complete Quaternary stratigraphic records in the world, including cyclic, dominantly shallow marine strata that record glacio-eustatic sea-level fluctuations (Pillans 2017). Our journey will take us through rural hill country and river valleys to witness landscapes and outcrops that have only emerged from the sea in the last 1 million years. The field trip follows a transect from Palmerston North through the Rangitikei and Pohangina valleys, with an overnight stay at Makoura Lodge. Stops have been selected to showcase key sedimentary units within the basin succession and explore the significance of these deposits for understanding basin history and the paleogeographic evolution of the lower North Island of Aotearoa New Zealand (Fig. 2).

We will track primary and reworked volcanoclastic marker horizons through the basin to witness how they are expressed across different depositional settings and how they can be used for correlation and stratigraphic interpretation. The deposits are all less than 3 million years old and provide a distal record of volcanic activity in the central North Island, including the initiation of the Taupō Volcanic Zone (TVZ) at ~2 Ma, which is considered to be the most productive silicic volcanic region in the world with at least 12 caldera forming eruptions producing over 3300 km³ DRE of magma over the last 350 ka (Houghton et al. 1995; Wilson et al. 1995; Kósik et al. 2020).

In addition, the trip will highlight river terraces preserved within actively uplifting landscapes that record partial inversion of the sedimentary basin and the interplay between sediment supply, stream power and base level associated with Quaternary climate events over the last ~350 thousand years. Overlying loess, tephra and paleosol coverbeds will be explored to gain insight into how these landforms are mapped and how they have formed through the late Quaternary.

The WB is also a cultural landscape of deep significance to Māori. Māori have deep ties to the land (whenua), viewing it as not just a physical place but as a spiritual ancestor (Papatūānuku) from whom all life originates, central to their identity and culture. A visit to Rātā Marae will provide us with an opportunity to appreciate the connection to the land and water that hosts this internationally important geological record.

A more detailed introduction to the WB and TVZ is provided in subsequent sections of this guide, followed by descriptions of each field trip stop, including the stratigraphy, age and key messages. Together, these stops offer a cross-section through the WB to explore how large-volume silicic volcanism has influenced sedimentation, stratigraphy, and geological interpretation within one of the world's premier Quaternary sedimentary basins.

Figure 1: The islands of Aotearoa New Zealand shown within the wider context of the Zealandia subcontinent. The Whanganui Basin (WB) is the focus of our field trip, located in the lower North Island of Aotearoa New Zealand. Contains information licensed under the NIWA Open Data License v1.0.

Figure 2: Map showing location of field field stops relative to the onland portion of the Whanganui Basin (WB). Field Trip Stops: 1) Waitapu Stream; 2) Otara Bridge; 3) Ruahine Road; 4) Table Flat Road; 5) Oroua Valley Lookout; 6) Finnis Road; 7) Broadlands Station; 8) Te Ahu a Turanga. A simplified cross section A to A' illustrates the undulating Mesozoic greywacke-argillite basement surface beneath the Late Miocene-Pleistocene basin fill, constrained by available borehole data. Data sourced from [Feldmeyer et al. \(1943\)](#); [Te Punga \(1952\)](#); [Fleming \(1953\)](#); [Milne \(1968\)](#); [Seward \(1974\)](#); [Anderton \(1981\)](#); [Melhuish et al. \(1996\)](#); [Pillans et al. \(2005\)](#); [Townsend et al. \(2008b\)](#); [Lee et al. \(2011\)](#) and [Rees et al. \(2018b\)](#).

Whanganui Basin

The islands of Aotearoa New Zealand are the surface expression of a large, mostly submerged subcontinent named 'Zealandia' that sits astride a convergent margin between the Pacific and Australian plates (Fig. 1) (Townsend et al. 2008a; Mortimer 2025). Subduction of the Pacific Plate and deformation of the overriding Australian Plate along the Hikurangi Trough, generates uplift, earthquakes and volcanic activity in the North Island (Fig. 2) (Henrys et al. 2025).

The Whanganui Basin (WB) basin lies ~200 km west of the Hikurangi Trough and is interpreted to have formed through a combination of lithospheric loading and compressional downwarping associated with coupling between the Pacific and Australian plates (Stern et al. 1993). WB basement rock consists primarily of Mesozoic greywacke-argillite (Mortimer et al. 1997). Over 4 km of subsidence has occurred since Late Miocene time. This accommodation space has been filled by sequences of largely marine Plio-Pleistocene sediments, including the type sections for the Aotearoa New Zealand Pleistocene and Upper Pliocene stages (Fleming 1953; Beu et al. 1987; Pillans 1991).

The basin fill is dominated by siliciclastic to bioclastic sediments deposited in coastal-plain, shoreface and shelf (0-200 m water depth) environments during climatically driven sea-level cycles (Abbott 1998; Carter & Naish 1998). Each cycle relates to a glacial/interglacial couplet, represented by vertically stacked, alternating, fine- and coarse-grained sedimentary units deposited during late sea-level rise, highstand and early fall stages (Appendix A). Lowstand intervals are marked by erosional surfaces formed during subaerial exposure of the continental shelf (Naish et al. 1998). The cyclothems correspond to fifth (100 ka)- and sixth (40 ka)-order sequences equivalent to odd-numbered oxygen isotope stages (interglacials). Seventy depositional cycles have been documented, correlated to Marine Isotope Stages (MIS) M2–3, spanning the last 3.3 million years (Carter & Naish 1998; Grant et al. 2018).

The basin fill is richly fossiliferous and many of the species continue to live around the Aotearoa New Zealand coastline, providing useful modern day analogues (Abbott & Carter 1994). Analysis of the molluscan and foraminiferal assemblages provides critical information on environments of deposition and is used together with magnetostratigraphy and tephrostratigraphy for regional correlation and linking the basin succession to the global marine isotope stages (Fleming 1953; Beu & Edwards 1984; Naish et al. 1998) (Appendix B).

The WB is bordered to the north by the Taupō Volcanic Zone (TVZ), the youngest volcanic zone in the central North Island's volcanic region. Voluminous, widespread welded and non-welded ignimbrites and airfall deposits originating from the TVZ have provided an important source of sediment to the WB over the last ~2 Ma (Carter 1972; Pillans 1991; Shane 1993; Shane et al. 1996).

Ongoing regional uplift (~0.3–0.5 m/ka along the modern coastline and ~1–3 m/ka adjacent to the axial range) and fluvial incision have produced exceptional on-land exposures through the gently southward-dipping basin succession (Anderton 1981; Pillans 1986; Pillans 2017) and resulted in a sequence of river terraces extending back ~350 thousand years (Milne 1973b). Loess, tephra and paleosol cover beds overlie the terraces, providing a means of dating and correlating the terraces across the landscape.

Figure 3: Key features of the North Island of Aotearoa New Zealand. AVF = Auckland Volcanic Field; CVR = Central Volcanic Region; CVZ = Coromandel Volcanic Zone; TVZ = Taupo Volcanic Zone; TgVC = Tongariro Volcanic Centre; EgVC = Egmont Volcanic Centre; NIDFB = North Island Dextral Fault Belt. Dashed black lines indicate location of the eight major rhyolitic calderas in the TVZ (Spinks et al. 2005). White dashed lines outline the CVR and North Island main axial ranges.

Taupō Volcanic Zone

The primary and reworked volcanoclastic deposits showcased on this field trip are related to one of the most dynamic subduction–rift transition settings on Earth. The central driver of this evolution is the Tonga–Kermadec arc–back-arc system, a 2800 km-long volcanic chain formed above the Pacific–Australian plate boundary, where subduction initiated south of Aotearoa New Zealand at ~2 Ma, giving rise to the modern Taupō Volcanic Zone (TVZ) at the southern termination of this system (Fig. 4).

However, the story recorded in the landscapes of the North Island begins much earlier. In the Early Miocene (23–18 Ma), subduction first built a SE–NW-striking volcanic arc across Northland. By 17 Ma, subduction in Northland shut down, followed by a major tectonic reorganisation: the plate boundary migrated eastward and restarted along the NEE-trending Colville–Lau arc, which remained active for more than 15 million years (~18–2 Ma).

From ~5.5 Ma, the Pacific Plate changed its rotation pole, triggering back-arc extension and rifting. This rifting split the Colville–Lau arc and shifted the volcanic front east, constructing the modern Kermadec arc and opening the Havre Trough back-arc basin behind it. The remnants of the older arc, now stranded on land, form the Coromandel Volcanic Zone (CVZ)—the eroded volcanic terrain is dominated by silicic and intermediate volcanic successions (andesite to rhyolite) that document sustained arc magmatism.

Since ~2 Ma, the locus of volcanic activity transitioned to the central North Island, where volcanism has been controlled by back-arc extension and caldera-dominated silicic eruptions. The Taupō Volcanic Zone (TVZ) is an active transtensional volcanic rift, developed on strongly thinned continental crust (15–20 km) above the subducting Hikurangi Plateau, an anomalously thick (15–25 km) oceanic igneous crustal block (Ballance 1976; Cole & Lewis 1981; Mortimer et al. 2010; Reyners 2013; Timm et al. 2014).

Extension in the TVZ is accommodated by a dense network of steep NNE–SSW-striking normal faults, with ongoing mantle melt input driving high magma productivity (Bibby et al. 1995; Rowland & Sibson 2001; Villamor & Berryman 2001; Harrison & White 2004; Stratford & Stern 2006; Reyners et al. 2007; Davy 2010). Fault-aligned vents and repeated caldera collapse cycles in the Mangakino, Kapenga, Whakamaru, Okataina and Taupō systems have governed the frequency, magnitude and dispersal of Quaternary explosive eruptions, generating widespread distal tephra marker horizons. These arc- and rift-sourced tephra beds are preserved across terrestrial and marine successions (Table 1), including the Whanganui Basin, which provides the key correlation framework for this excursion (Table 2).

Figure 4: The main volcanic and tectonic framework of the Miocene Coromandel Volcanic Zone (CVZ) and the Quaternary Taupō Volcanic Zone (TVZ). Major calderas of the older and younger TVZ are labelled (*Ma* – Mangakino; *Ka* – Kapenga; *Wh* – Whakamaru; *Wha* – Ohakuri; *Ro* – Rotorua; *Rp* – Reporoa; *Ok* – Okataina; *Tp* – Taupō), together with the youngest preserved CVZ caldera (*Kai* – Kaimai Volcanic Centre). Offshore structures in the Bay of Plenty follow [Wright \(1992\)](#) and the TVZ boundary is after [Wilson et al. \(1995\)](#). The map is modified from [Briggs et al. \(2005\)](#) and complemented with stratigraphic and volcanic constraints from the GNS 1:250,000 map series ([Edbrooke 2001, 2005](#); [Townsend et al. 2008b](#); [Leonard et al. 2010](#); [Lee et al. 2011](#)).

Table 1: Stratigraphic relationship, source and estimated volumes of large-volume, caldera-forming eruptions of the TVZ. DRE volume estimates for most deposits are based on known mapped extents and recorded thicknesses that are converted, assuming that bulk volumes are equivalent to magma volumes when erosion and co-eruptive fall deposits now missing are taken into account (Wilson et al. 2009). The age of eruptions was compiled from: 1 – Wilson et al. (2009); 2 – Leonard et al. (2010); 3 – Deering et al. (2011); 4 – Danisik et al. (2012); 5 – Downs et al. (2014); 6 – Gravelly et al. (2016).

Name	Source caldera	Age (ka)	Age error	Dating method	DRE volume (km ³)	Reference
Taupo Pumice F	Taupo	1.8	0.05	C14	35	1
Oruanui Formation	Taupo	25.4	0.2	C14	530	5
Rotoiti Formation	Okataina	45 or 61	1.4		80	1, 4
Mokai	uncertain	210	6	Ar/Ar	40	1
Kaingaroa Formation	Reporoa	281	21	Ar/Ar	100	1
Ohakuri Formation	Ohakuri	~280-290		Ar/Ar	100	1, 5
Mamaku Plateau F.	Rotorua	~280-290		Ar/Ar	145	1, 5
Pokai Formation	Kapenga	~300		Ar/Ar	100	1, 5
Chimpanzee Formation	Kapenga	uncertain			50	1, 5
Matahina Formation	Okataina	322	7	Ar/Ar	150	1, 5
Whakamaru Group, Paeroa Subgroup	Whakamaru	339	5	Ar/Ar	110	5, 6
Whakamaru Group F.	Whakamaru	349	4	Ar/Ar	2200	5, 6
Utu ignimbrite	Okataina	~549		Ar/Ar	90	3
Waiotapu Formation	Kapenga	710	60	K/Ar	100	1
Rahopaka	?Kapenga	720	30	K/Ar	30	1
Tikorangi	?Kapenga	890	40	K/Ar	30	1
Marshall Formation	?Mangakino	950	30	K/Ar	50	1
Akatarewa ignimbrite	uncertain	950	50	K/Ar		5
Rocky Hill ignimbrite	Mangakino	1000	50	K/Ar	200	1
Kidnappers ignimbrite	Mangakino	1010	10	K/Ar	1200	1
Ahuroa ignimbrite	Mangakino	1180	20	K/Ar	100	1
Unit D	?Mangakino	1200	40	K/Ar	100	1
Ongatiti Formation	Mangakino	1210	40	K/Ar	400	1
Unit C (Pouakani F.)	Mangakino	1400	100	K/Ar	50	1, 2
Unit B (Tolley F.)	?Mangakino	1530	40	K/Ar	100	1, 2
Ngaroma Formation	?Mangakino	1550	50	K/Ar	100	1
Unit F (Link Formation)	uncertain	1600	90	K/Ar	30	1,2
Torlesse Subgroup (metasedimentary basement rocks)		Late Jurassic				5

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Table 2: Selected tephra-fall and/or volcanoclastic deposits and their respective stratigraphic units from the Rangitikei. Ages derived from Alloway et al. (2004), Pillans et al. (1994), Naish et al. (1996), Shane et al. (1996), Seward and Kohn (1997), Naish et al. (1998), McIntyre (2002), Pillans et al. (2005) and Grant et al. (2018).

Group	Formation	Member	Tephra-fall and/or volcanoclastic deposit	ITPFT age (Ma)	Zircon FT age (Ma)	Astronomical age (Ma)	U-Th-Pb and U-Pb age (Ma)
Shakespeare	Mangatapu	Rangitawa Pumice	Rangitawa	0.34 ± 0.03		0.35	
	Tokorangi		Onepuhi			0.57	
Kai Iwi	Reu Reu						
	Waiomio	Waiomio Shellbed	Kupe	0.63 ± 0.08		0.65	
		Waitapu Shell Conglomerate	Kaukatea	0.86 ± 0.08		0.90	
	Kaimatira Pumice Sand	Potaka Pumice	Potaka	1.00 ± 0.03	0.97 ± 0.04	0.99	
Okehu	Rewa	Rewa Pumice	Rewa	1.20 ± 0.14	1.00 ± 0.06	1.19	
	Makirikiri Tuff	Mangapipi	Mangapipi Ridge	1.51 ± 0.16	1.26 ± 0.08	1.54	
		Pakihikura Pumice	Pakihikura	1.58 ± 0.08	1.66 ± 0.07	1.60	
Maxwell	Upper Maxwell		Birdgrove			1.60	
			Mangahaou			1.63	
			Maranoa			1.64	
			Ototoka	1.72 ± 0.32		1.64	
			Table Flat	1.71 ± 0.12		1.65	
Rangitikei	Rataiti						
	Vinegar Hill Formation	Waipuru Shellbed	Vinegar Hill	1.75 ± 0.20	1.73 ± 0.08	1.75	
	Mangaonoho	Mangamako Shellbed	Waipuru	1.79 ± 0.15		1.83	
			Mangamako			2.05	
	Orangipongo	Ohingaiti Sand	Ohingaiti			2.17	
	Makohine	Tuha Sand					
	Tikapu	Hautawa Shellbed					
	Mangarere	Te Rimu Sand					
Paparangi	Mangaweka Mudstone Formation		Eagle Hill		2.7 ± 0.3	2.88	2.85 ± 0.2
			Kowhai			2.88	
Utiku	Manui		Siberia			3.12	3.12 ± 0.18

DAY 1

STOP 1 – Waitapu Stream

Stop 1 is located 37 km northwest of Palmerston North City in the Waitapu Stream Valley, a tributary of the Rangitikei River. The area contains the type section for the Waitapu Shell Conglomerate (~0.9 Ma), a cross-bedded pebbly-shell conglomerate containing the first influx of Kaukatea Pumice (~0.9 Ma) within the Rangitikei succession.

The fossil assemblage contains a mixture of estuarine to offshore species including a component derived from underlying rocks ([Appendix C and D](#)). Deposition is thought to have taken place seaward of a transgressive shoreline on a storm-dominated, muddy, innermost shelf (<25 m water depth), characterised by migrating gravel dunes interfingering with deeper water heterolithic facies. The abundance of fresh pumice and charcoal indicates deposition closely followed a major TVZ eruption within a phase of renewed volcanic activity from the Mangakino Volcanic Centre at ~0.9 Ma.

Walking up the Waitapu Stream we climb stratigraphically through a full sedimentary cycle. We start at the Waitapu Shell Conglomerate, representing shallow, high energy, innermost shelf (<25 m water depth) deposition. This transitions into massive to laminated siltstone deposited in mid shelf (50-100 m water depth) environments. Towards the end of the walk, we will see an erosional unconformity and overlying shellbed representing the base of the next cycle.

The ~0.9 Ma Waitapu Shell Conglomerate occurs during the Mid-Pleistocene Transition, when Earth's climate shifted from high frequency, low amplitude 41 ka cycles, thought to relate to the tilt of the earth's axis (obliquity) into lower frequency, higher amplitude 100 ka cycles matching the Earth's eccentricity cycle. Various theories have been proposed to explain this transition; however, scientists still do not have a clear answer. It possibly relates to declining atmospheric CO² levels and increased bedrock-ice friction after regolith removal ([Willeit et al. 2019](#)) making the climate system more sensitive to orbital forcing and allowing larger ice sheets to form and amplify the 100 ka signal.

Stratigraphy

The Waitapu Shell Conglomerate ([Fig. 5](#)) contains a heterolithic mixture of bioclastic and siliciclastic sediments, with clasts typically of pebble size in a matrix of coarse sands and granules. The basal contact is erosive with channels up to 1 m deep carved into the underlying laminated to lenticular bedded siltstone and fine sandstone. Large-scale, low-angle, trough cross-bedded sets 1-2 m thick contain large (up to 400 mm), angular rip-up clasts of the laminated to lenticular bedded siltstone and fine sandstone. Lenses of siltstone, 0.1 – 0.3 m thick, drape the crossbeds, pinching out laterally. The rip-up clasts contain original laminated to lenticular bedding formed prior to reworking and appear to be derived from the heterolithic beds immediately beneath the cross-bedded sets.

Clasts are dominantly pebbles of sub-rounded, disc to blade-shaped, greywacke, pumice, rhyolite and ignimbrite 2–64 mm in diameter, with rare larger clasts >100 mm.

Figure 5. Stratigraphic log of the type section for the Waitapu Shell Conglomerate near the mouth of Waitapu Stream, Rangitikei Valley (BL34 1582 6596) and other laterally equivalent sections from across the basin. Data sourced from Kershaw (1989), Abbott (1994), van der Neut (1996), Pillans et al. (2005), Rees et al. (2018c), Rees et al. (2019).

Clasts are typically weakly aligned along the cross-bed sets. Rare charcoal is particularly evident within the lower-most channelled cross-bed sets, occurring as pockets of rounded clasts up to 70 mm in diameter. Variable concentration and composition of clasts occurs throughout the deposit, with particular cross-bedded sets enriched in bioclastic material, greywacke pebbles and pumiceous alluvium.

Bioclastic material is highly worn, comprising approximately equal proportions of granule-sized debris and variably preserved fossil Mollusca dominated by *Paphies sp.* Particular lenses of highly enriched bioclastic material occur, in which shell fragments and whole shells comprise up to 80% of the material in a siliciclastic matrix. Similarly, other lenses are enriched in pumiceous sediment containing abundant sub-rounded pumice clasts up to 150 mm in diameter. The largest pumice clasts significantly outsize clasts of any other lithology.

A gradual fining upward sequence occurs above the Waitapu Shell Conglomerate, changing from heterolithic sediments with rare shell debris to massive, sparsely fossiliferous siltstone. Overlying the fine-grained massive siltstone is a conglomeratic unit. The base is characterised by a 1 m thick, well sorted, un-fossiliferous, clast-supported greywacke conglomerate overlain by coarse to granule sandstone. A cross-bedded shell conglomerate, locally scours into this greywacke conglomerate-sandstone unit. The first appearance of *Pecten novaezelandiae* within the shell conglomerate allows correlation to the Kaikokopu Shell Grit ([Abbott 1994](#)).

Two distinctive beds of soft sediment deformation, 0.3 and 0.6 m thick, occur within a highly variable succession of alternating lenticular fine sandstone and siltstone with rare, thin lenses of shell debris. These beds are characterised by ball and pillow structures comprising fine sandstone to siltstone tightly folded into concentric layers with some lateral variation in grain-size and patterns of deformation.

Depositional Environment

The Waitapu Shell Conglomerate contains fossils representative of a wide variety of depositional environments. Shells are well mixed, broken and abraded, typical of reworking by waves and tidal currents. Trough cross-bedding indicates dune bed forms produced by strong unidirectional currents ([Harms et al. 1982](#); [Duke et al. 1991](#)). Set thicknesses of up to 2 m implies the influence of strong tidal and/or storm-driven currents ([Abbott 1998](#); [Le Bot & Trentsaux 2004](#)). Mud draped crossbed foresets indicate fluctuating energy conditions, including slack water/quiescent periods where finer particles settled from suspension. The channelled erosion surface below the crossbed sets was likely formed by strong storm/tidal action, possibly related to a reduction in the mean wave base and localised scour and fill of sediments ([Dott & Bourgeois 1982](#)).

The Waitapu Shell Conglomerate is analogous to the basal TST shell conglomerates described at the Castlecliff section ([Abbott 1998](#)), interpreted to represent deposition on a storm-dominated, muddy innermost shelf ([Abbott & Carter 1994](#)). We infer the presence of a fluvial outlet in close proximity to the depositional site, with headwaters located in the present day central North Island, supplying abundant greywacke and volcanoclastic detritus to the coast. This is consistent with the lateral changes observed within the Waitapu Shell Conglomerate, as it grades into an eastern margin conglomerate facies, characterised by a lack of marine fossils and rare lignite, suggesting closer proximity to fluvial systems draining the uplifting paleo-axial range.

At the WBs eastern margin, we envision braid plains, delta fronts and gravelly beaches to have developed during sea level low stand, locally incising through the previous HST, as evidenced by delta type architecture above undulating surfaces of erosion within eastern margin conglomerate deposits (Fig. 6). Nearby land was likely deforested and sediment input was particularly high (Beu et al. 1981; Lewis et al. 1994). Low stand deposits were later scoured and eroded during transgressive ravinement, reworked into shelly gravel dunes at inner-most shelf depths (Abbott 1998). Local preservation of low stand deposits in eastern WB (Abbott 1992), suggests transgressive ravinement was either not as destructive or that low stand incision was more pervasive along the eastern basin margin. Marine transgression and associated shoreface retreat triggered sedimentary infilling of the valleys incised during the previous low stand (Rees et al. 2018c). Estuarine systems developed, hosting a wide range of species, including *Cyclomactra tristis*, *Austrovenus stutchburyi*, *Paphies australis* and *Cominella adspersa*, the shells of which were transported into the marine environment by rivers (Hayward & Stilwell 1995) or became entrained during transgressive ravinement and sedimentary reworking (Abbott 1998).

The abundant unweathered pumice within the Waitapu Shell conglomerate is typically of a much larger clast size than the accompanying clasts of greywacke, suggesting that a phase of important eruptions in the TVZ preceded and perhaps accompanied its deposition (Te Punga 1952). This is consistent with the incorporation of clasts of charcoal within the lowest beds of the Waitapu Shell Conglomerate.

Figure 6: Schematic cartoon of the WB during the marine transgression of WB cycle 36 (MIS 22) at c. 0.88 Ma (Bowen et al. 1998; Lisiecki & Raymo 2005).

Rātā Marae Lunch

We will visit Rātā Marae for a pōwhiri (traditional Māori welcome ceremony) and lunch. This will be followed by a discussion and introduction to the area to gain some insight into the significance of the sites we will visit during our trip.

STOP 2 – Otara Bridge

Otara bridge provides an excellent opportunity to see the Tuha/Hautawa Shellbed which is one of the most important shell beds in the WB. It provides the earliest evidence for cooling in Aotearoa New Zealand marine deposits, correlated to when the first continental ice sheets started to form in the northern hemisphere, evidenced by the first ice rafted debris in the north Atlantic (Evans et al. 2024).

Biostratigraphy has been used to correlate Aotearoa New Zealand stratigraphy with the international geological timescale; however, fine scale correlation has proven difficult due to the significant endemism of Aotearoa New Zealand fauna and flora (Beu 2001; Cooper 2004). This creates a need for a local timescale (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Chronostratigraphy (Pillans 2017). GPTS Geomagnetic Polarity Time Scale.

The Hautawa Shellbed has been used to mark the base of the Aotearoa New Zealand Nukumaruan Stage at the first incoming of *Zygochlamys delicatula* (Fig. 8) and the subantarctic crab *Jacquinitia edwardsii* into the WB and east coast basin (Fleming 1944, 1953; Beu et al. 1977). However, the Hautawa Shellbed is slightly younger than the international Plio-Pleistocene boundary set at 2.58 Ma, defined by the Global Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP) Monte San Nicola section in Sicily, Italy, close to the Gauss/Matuyama boundary (Gibbard et al. 2009). In Aotearoa New Zealand, the Plio-Pleistocene boundary, approximated by the Gauss/Matuyama polarity reversal, occurs in the top of the Mangaweka Mudstone, ~280 m below the Hautawa Shellbed (Naish et al. 1997).

The Tuha Shellbed is one cycle above the the Hautawa Shellbed and is a mollusc rich coquina shellbed in a matrix of siliciclastic fine silty sandstone. The sedimentology and faunal content dominated by *Zygochlamys delicatula*, *Talochlamys gemmulata*, *Tawera subsulcata*, *Pleuromeris hectori*, *Ostrea chilensis* and *Brachiopoda* suggests deposition within an open marine inner shelf environment where terrigenous sediment bypass and stratigraphic condensation was taking place during a marine transgression (Fleming 1953; Naish & Kamp 1995) (Fig. 9).

Figure 8: Cool water scallop Zygochlamys delicatula collected from the Hautawa Shellbed Type Section in the WB (Left) (Beu 1995) and an illustration of Zygochlamys delicatula from Beu and Maxwell (1990) (Right).

Figure 9: Stratigraphic log of Cycle 3 from the Rangitikei section, Makohine Formation (Dunbar & Barrett 2005). Lithology and paleobathymetry from Naish and Kamp (1996); Naish and Kamp (1997a); Naish and Kamp (1997b). Textural estimates based on assumption that wave climate is similar to current day Manawatū Coast where the mean fair weather wave base is ~25 m and the mean storm wave base is ~40 m.

STOP 3 – Ruahine Road

Stop 3 along Ruahine Road provides excellent exposure through the ~400 m thick Mangaweka Mudstone (~2.5 – 3 Ma; Paparangi Group). Although this stratigraphic unit appears to be a somewhat monotonous blue grey mudstone, detailed work investigating changes in grain size, remnant paleomagnetism and fossil content has identified evidence of seven sea level cycles and the base of the Quaternary at the ~2.58 Ma Gauss-Matuyama reversal (normal to reverse polarity) at the top of Cycle 10 (Fig. 10) (Journeaux et al. 1996; Turner et al. 2005) .

The siliciclastic mudstones in the WB are weakly magnetised and are prone to diagenetic alternation due to the movement of fluids through the sediments and growth of authigenic minerals. Authigenic minerals acquire their remnant magnetisation later than the original detrital grains, complicating the study of the primary component of magnetisation (Turner et al. 2005).

Immediately below the Mangaweka Mudstone are sandstones of the Utiku Group (~3 – 3.5 Ma) which represent innermost shelf environments (~5-25 m) during a phase where sediment supply outpaced subsidence in the WB. A phase of tectonically driven subsidence and rapid deepening occurred at ~3 Ma with the lower Mangaweka Mudstone being deposited in outer shelf depths (~150-200 m) (Journeaux 1995). Mica flakes >2mm in size are present in the Utiku Group sandstones suggesting that at the time of deposition South Island granite and schist provided an important sediment source.

The Eagle Hill (~13 cm thick) and underlying Kowhai (~5 cm) tephra's are exposed in the Mangaweka Mudstone along Ruahine Road (Journeaux et al. 1996; Naish et al. 1996). Both tephra are disrupted by bioturbation with burrows up to ~20 cm in length present. Naish et al. (1996) presents an age of ~2.88 Ma for both tephra's based on their stratigraphic position and estimated sedimentation rates. Electron microprobe data from Naish et al. (1996) reveals that both tephra's contain single glass populations, implying they were erupted from single events. Grant et al. (2018) presents a zircon fission-track age of 2.7 ± 0.3 Ma for the Eagle Hill Tephra.

A vertical separation of ~8 m suggests a difference in age of ~8 ka based on an estimated sedimentation rate of ~1mm/year (Naish et al. 1996). The presence of the mollusc *Nemocardium pulchellum* and foraminifera *Anomalinoidea sp.*, *Bolivinita pliozea*, and *Nonionella flemingi* in the succession suggest that the tephra's settled onto an open marine outer shelf at ~100-200 m water depth (Journeaux 1995). Both tephra's are considered too old to be sourced from the Taupō Volcanic Zone and are probably distally sourced from the Coromandel Volcanic Zone (Dickinson et al. 2008).

Figure 10: Stratigraphic log of the Mangaweka Mudstone. Changes in texture reveal seven sea level cycles (Journeaux 1995; Journeaux et al. 1996).

Stratigraphically below the Eagle Hill and Kowhai tephra we see a zone of concretionary mudstone. These concretions form in the saturated sediments deposited on the seafloor, where lime rich pore water precipitates calcite crystals, filling pore space around a 'core' of stone, shell or bone, growing from a central portion outward in all directions to form a spherical shape. Where the sediment is less uniform the concretions can become elongated along one axis as commonly seen in the Rangitikei (Fig. 11).

Figure 11: The formation of concretions in saturated sediments on the sea floor (Ballance 2009)

Makoura Lodge Accomodation

We will be spending the night in shared accommodation at Makoura Lodge, 736 Makoura Road, Feilding 4771. Makoura Lodge is situated on a Last Glacial river terrace along Mākiekie (Coal) Creek, a tributary of the Pohangina River, which has its headwaters in the Ruahine Range. The 'coal' name likely originates from the lignite beds that occur within the Plio-Pleistocene sediments of the WB in this area.

If time allows, we will visit the caves near the end of Table Flat Road. These caves are developed in Table Flat Shell Conglomerate (~7-10m thick). [Milne \(1968\)](#) noted *Zygochlamys delicatula*, *Crassostrea ingens* and *Phialopecten triphooki* in this unit, suggesting an earliest Nukumaruan age. The Table Flat Shell Conglomerate can be tentatively correlated to the Te Apiti Conglomerate at Stop 8 and the Hautawa Shellbed. The presence of greywacke pebbles within the shellbed suggests some greywacke-argillite was elevated along the paleo-Ruahine Ranges at this time.

The shell conglomerate likely formed in shallow (5-30 m), high energy marine environment where wave action and currents crushed and concentrated bioclastic material in shoal areas and winnowed out finer sediments, transporting them into deeper water environments. More delicate shells have become crushed and incorporated into the matrix.

DAY 2**STOP 4 – Table Flat Road**

Table Flat Road provides a good opportunity to see an exposure through the Porewa (Pourewa) Terrace formed during MIS 4, ~70-80 ka. At the base of the section we see several metres of Porewa (Pourewa) aggradational gravels deposited ~70-80 ka (Fig. 12). Overlying the greywacke gravel is weathered tephra from the central North Island mixed with Porewa (Pourewa) alluvium. The Kimbolton Paleosol occurs at the top of the tephra with weathering evidenced by its strong brown colour (Leamy et al. 1973). Rata (Rātā) loess (~30-50 ka) and the Whanahuia Paleosol occur above the tephra, with the paleosol displaying characteristic abundant yellowish red oxide rhizomorphs and iron oxide lenses. The upper part of the profile contains the ~25.5 ka Kawakawa Tephra (Vandergoes et al. 2013; Dunbar et al. 2017) enclosed in Ohakea Loess (~10-30 ka).

Stop 4 has good visibility along the road and room to move aside if traffic is encountered. The outcrop does require some climbing to access the coverbeds up close. Samples of the ~25.5 ka Kawakawa Tephra will be taken and handed around to those who wish to remain on the roadside.

An airfall pumiceous tephra occurs at high points in the landscape along Table Flat Road at ~0.5 m depth. It is not observed at the cuts on Table Flat Road but can be found if you auger down on nearby topographic highs. This tephra is tentatively correlated to the Waimihia Tephra (3.4 ka) (Pizer et al. 2023) but requires microprobe work to confirm. Tephra is an important component of the parent material along Table Flat Road.

At Stop 5 we will look back (east) across the Oroua River Valley and see the MIS 4 terraces capping the modern Pohangina-Oroua interfluvium. These terraces were created by the Oroua River ~70-80 ka and demonstrate how young and active the landscapes are against the foot of the Ruahine Range where uplift of up to ~1–3 m/ka is occurring (Pillans 1986).

Figure 12: Stratigraphic profile for the Porewa (Pourewa) 2 Terrace (MIS 4 ~70-80 ka) outcropping along Table Flat Road (E 1853144, N 5573277, NZTM).

STOP 5 – Oroua Valley Lookout

Turning off onto Kimbolton Road from Kiwitea we have been slowly climbing higher in elevation as we travel along an Aldworth River terrace, formed during MIS 10 ~345 ka. Although there is no distinct terrace riser around Kimbolton, regional mapping by [Lee et al. \(2011\)](#) suggests the Oroua Valley Lookout is located on the Ararata marine terrace formed during MIS 11 ~400 ka, consistent with drill core interpretation by [Qizhong et al. \(1992\)](#).

The Oroua Valley Lookout is located just north of Kimbolton and provides a view east across the Oroua Valley towards the Ruahine Range. MIS 2, 3 and 4 river terraces can be seen preserved along the Oroua Valley ([Fig. 13](#)). We visited an outcrop through a MIS 4 terrace at Stop 4 to see the aggradational gravel alluvium and overlying loess, tephra and paleosol coverbeds that assist with relative dating and correlation.

The overgrown cutting immediately west of the lookout is the type section for the Kimbolton Paleosol, developed in Upper Tongaririo Subgroup tephra on Porewa (Pourewa) loess ([Leamy et al. 1973](#)). This is a reasonably quiet country road, however, the cut is located on a corner with poor visibility and very little room to make way for traffic, making it unsafe to approach as a group.

A 11.2 m deep core was taken 1.5 km north of the Oroua Valley Lookout near the Kimbolton cemetery and described by Hugh Wilde and Dennis Eden in 1990 and later published in [Qizhong et al. \(1992\)](#). The core encountered the ~25.5 Kawakawa Tephra ([Vandergoes et al. 2013](#); [Dunbar et al. 2017](#)) and ~345 ka Rangitawa Tephra ([Pillans et al. 1996](#)) interbedded with loess sheets, finishing in very sticky, light olive-grey clayey sediments with distinct horizontal veins that were interpreted to be of possible lacustrine origin.

Loess, paleosol, and tephra horizons within the coverbeds can be difficult to see by eye and often dry bulk density, water content, atterberg limits, penetrometer and total element analysis are undertaken to help with description. In particular, potassium has been found to be a sensitive indicator of paleosol development ([Childs & Searle 1975](#); [Milne & Smalley 1979](#)).

Formation of the Rangitikei-Manawatū river terraces

Stadial phases in the lower North Island were characterised by an almost complete switch from full forest cover to shrub and grassland with only isolated beech and podocarp refugia able to survive ([Milne 1973a](#); [Newnham et al. 2013](#)). Cool temperatures caused a lowering of the treeline, created more bare ground, and enhanced frost-cracking, which drove enhanced physical weathering, production of regolith and increased sediment supply to rivers and streams ([Milne 1973a](#)).

Lower precipitation and stream power combined with higher sediment supply caused aggradation, forming wide multi-threaded floodplains similar to the Waimakariri River on the Canterbury Plains today. We see evidence of these former multi-threaded floodplains preserved on Last Glacial river terraces in the Rangitikei Valley. During aggradational phases, loess is blown from the floodplain and deposited across the surrounding landscape, becoming preserved on older, higher and more stable landscape surfaces (Vella 1963; Palmer & Pillans 1996).

Interglacial and interstadial phases are characterised by increased vegetation cover, landscape stabilisation and reduced sediment supply, allowing the river to begin transporting its imposed sediment load and have excess power to cut down into the landscape. Enhanced precipitation and stream power allows the rivers to flush excess gravel and begin to rapidly cut down through the soft rock of the WB.

Uplift continues slowly through time and eventually, the remnants of an abandoned aggradation plain are preserved within the wider valley, as the river becomes entrenched in a new degradational floodplain. The terraces become gently tilted as they are uplifted, resulting in the treads of older terraces occurring at progressively higher elevation and steeper dip ($0.3\text{--}1^\circ$) within the landscape (Milne 1973a). The extent of fluvial dissection intensifies with increasing terrace age, such that the oldest terraces occur as highly dissected remnants between deeply incised valleys with high drainage density. The most widespread and best preserved terraces in the Rangitikei Valley are the Ohakea Terraces associated with the LGM. Not only was this a pronounced phase of aggradation, but it has also been subject to the least amount of subsequent fluvial dissection and lateral corrasion.

Figure 13: Annotated view from the Oroua Valley lookout showing the Porewa (Pourewa) Terrace (MIS 4, 70-80 ka) and Ohakea Terrace (MIS 2, 10-30 ka) in the Oroua Valley (Central Economic Development Agency, 2021 - ManawatuNZ.co.nz).

STOP 6 – Finnis Road

Stop 6 takes us northward up the Pohangina Valley, to a deeply incised gully system that exposes weakly consolidated to unconsolidated ~1.2 – 1 Ma sedimentary units on the western limb of the Pohangina Anticline (Figs. 2 and 14).

Stratigraphy

The Rewa Pumice (~1.2 Ma) occurs at the base of the Finnis Road section in parallel bedded pumiceous sand with occasional cross bed sets. There is ~80 m of sediment between the base of the section and the Potaka Pumice (~1 Ma) near the top of the section, which contrasts markedly with the ~40 m of sediment between these same beds seen at Stop 7, ~13 km to the south. Between these two pumiceous rich units are a range of predominantly sandy units with occasional silt and mud lenses and scattered greywacke pebbles occur. Sedimentary structures are dominated by parallel beds but also include flaser, lenticular and convolute beds, ripples, cross bedding, rip up clasts and small channels (up to 1 m wide and 15 cm deep with common rip up clasts). The top of the section is characterised by a sudden influx of pumiceous rich material and contains a variety of sandy units with common cross bedding and small pebble to granule sized, sub-rounded clasts of pumice.

This interval of predominantly parallel bedded, sandy sediments between the Rewa and Potaka pumices has been interpreted to represent shallow marine deposition, possibly in a nearshore to beach type environment (Brackley 1999). This is consistent with the occurrence of shellbeds below and above the Rewa Pumice in nearby sections (Townsend 1993). The occurrence of lignite and rootlets in the Beehive Creek section provides some evidence of terrestrial conditions; these deposits are particularly common following deposition of the Potaka Pumice at ~1 Ma.

Sedimentary response to ignimbrite emplacement involves inundation of river and coastal settings, causing valley aggradation, river avulsion, infilling of coastal embayment's and coastal progradation (Manville & Wilson 2004; Kataoka 2011). A dramatic flood of volcanoclastic sediment entered the WB at ~1 Ma (Potaka Pumice of Te Punga, 1952). This influx of volcanoclastic sediment forms one of the thickest transgressive system tracts (TST) documented within the WB (TST's typically <30 m, but Kaimatira Pumice Sand TST is 80 m+ in the Rangitikei), resulting in coastal progradation (Lewis 2007). Common convolute bedding during this interval have been suggested to be a result of increased sedimentation characterised by an abundance of unstable, water saturated sediment entering the basin, creating a hydraulically active seafloor environment (Abbott & Carter 1999).

Several authors suggest the presence of a nearby fluvial outlet supplying abundant volcanoclastic and siliciclastic sediment to the marginal to shallow marine environments (Townsend 1993; Brackley 1999; Rees et al. 2019). Evidence of possible fluvial reworking includes channel structures and rip up clasts of siltstone and lignite (Brackley 1999). East of the Rangitikei greywacke conglomerates begin to occur around the Potaka and Kaukatea pumices ~ 1 Ma and have a distinct lack of any bioclastic material. West of the Rangitikei-Oroua interfluvium the equivalent conglomerate units contain abundant crushed shell material.

Anticlines

The Manawatu plains contain a series of approximately NE-SW trending anticlines, including the Pohangina, Feilding, Marton, Mt Stewart-Halcombe, and Oroua anticlines (Fig. 14). These anticlines were first documented in published work by Feldmeyer et al. (1943) and Te Punga (1952, 1957). They are bounded on their eastern flank by westward dipping reverse faults that only rarely reach the surface (Begg et al. 2005) and have been identified by seismic reflection surveys (Feldmeyer et al. 1943; Anderton 1981; Melhuish et al. 1996; Jackson et al. 1998; Nicol & Beavan 2003; Lamarche et al. 2005). The anticlines are asymmetric, characterised by gentle western slopes (typically 2-5°) and steep eastern slopes (up to 70°).

Their asymmetric geometry is interpreted to reflect the westward dipping, shallow reverse faults beneath (Jackson et al. 1998). Feldmeyer et al. (1943) and Te Punga (1957) both suggested that these anticlines were formed by ridges of basement rock trending approximately parallel with the main axial range. Structural interpretation of the Whanganui-Manawatu area indicates that these folds are still actively growing (Jackli 1957; Te Punga 1957; Lensen 1977). Preservation of the ~310 ka Brunswick marine terrace tread (Pillans 1983; Pillans 2017) on the anticlines together with seismic reflection evidence of faulting within underlying Plio-Pleistocene sediments (Melhuish et al. 1996) suggests these features are long lived and have been growing since at least Pliocene time with a majority of the present day topography forming over the last ~300 ka.

Figure 14: 3D image of the Whanganui-Manawatu area showing major rivers and anticlines across the Manawatu Plains. DEM sourced from LINZ, 2016.

Raumai Reserve Lunch

We will be stopping at Raumai Reserve to have lunch beside the Pohangina River. There are toilets located at the reserve; however, they are long drops. We will stop at Woodville on the way to our Stop 8 so that you can use flushing toilets if you prefer. In the cliffs beside the river, we can see a Last Glacial river terrace characterised by aggradational gravels overlying an erosional unconformity or strath. Underlying the gravels we see blue grey mudstone of the WB, thought to be stratigraphically below the Potaka Pumice at ~1.2 Ma.

STOP 7 – Broadlands Station

Stop 7 is located 25 km northeast of Palmerston North City and is characterised by a Plio-Pleistocene sedimentary record resting unconformably on Mesozoic greywacke-argillite of the Torlesse Composite Terrane. The main axial range, a geologically young piercement structure that has undergone a majority of its uplift over the last 1 Ma, is bound by major regional structures trending approximately NE-SW that act to deform the overlying Plio-Pleistocene succession into a sharp monocline (Beu et al. 1981; Shane 1991; Trewick & Bland 2012; Rees et al. 2018b) (Figs. 2 and 14).

Stratigraphy

The geology of the area has been documented in stratigraphic studies by Ower (1943), Rich (1959), Piyasin (1966), Carter (1972), Finlayson (1980), Marden (1984), Beanland (1995), Milner (2017) and Rees et al. (2018b). The Plio-Pleistocene sediments of the Pohangina Valley have been subdivided into the Komako, Konewa and Takapari formations, in order of decreasing age (Carter 1972). A key feature of the younger Takapari Formation is the episodic occurrence of volcanoclastic deposits that have been fluvially transported into coastal plain to shallow marine environments following voluminous volcanic eruptions originating from the TVZ (Fig. 15). At this time the direction of fluvial transport to the area was to the south to southeast, as evidenced by the paleo-current work of Brackley (1999).

During the Early Quaternary, marine basins existed on both sides of the modern-day main axial range (Fig. 16), connected by marine seaways (Beu et al. 1981; Browne 1986, 2004; Rees et al. 2018a). Progressive retreat of the sea at ~1.6 Ma is indicated in the Pohangina area by a change from shallow marine sedimentation to intermittent influxes of volcanoclastics within fluvio-estuarine environments. East-west drainage developed ~1 Ma, including ponding near Woodville from which an early ancestor of the Manawatu River exited, establishing an antecedent path to the Tasman Sea across the uplifting paleo-axial range.

Castlecliffian strata preserved within the lower Pohangina Valley have been correlated to Takapari Formation of Carter (1972) in mapping by Rees et al. (2018b). Identification of the widespread ~1 Ma Potaka Pumice (Te Punga 1952; Pillans 2017) within the Pohangina Valley succession has allowed an upper contact to be set for the Takapari Formation of Carter (1972), providing a direct link to the lower boundary of the Kaimatira Pumice Sand Formation of Fleming (1953).

Figure 15: Stratigraphic column of Takapari Formation exposed on Awahou South Road, Broadlands Station, lower Pohangina Valley (NZGD2000 -40.280017 S, 175.773869 E).

The Takapari Formation, cropping out in Pohangina Valley, consists of sandy mudstones, sandstones and shellbeds interbedded with vitric volcanoclastic sandstone and carbonaceous mudstone. The lower Waitokanui Member is composed of laminated sandy mudstone with lenses of siltstone and fossiliferous horizons. This unit is unconformably overlain by the Awahou Member, comprising a succession of coarse to fine grained sandstones interbedded with massive siltstone and laminated mudstone. Pumice first appears in bed 9 and 10 of the presented section (Fig. 15), defining the base of Awahou Member. The volcanoclastic units occur in close association with high energy bed forms, such as cross bedding with erosional lower contacts, overlain by carbonaceous mudstone and common thin beds of lignite.

STOP 8 – Te Ahu a Turanga

Stop 8 is located along the \$824 M Te Ahu a Turanga – Manawatū Tararua Highway that opened in June 2025, replacing the old Manawatū gorge road which closed in 2017 due to ongoing landslides. The project involved >6 Mm³ of earthworks, including cuts up to ~55 m high (Waka Kotahi, 2025). The highway provides a new route across the Ruahine Range which is critical for local communities, businesses and freight.

The highway crosses the Manawatū Saddle, a structural low in the underlying Mesozoic greywacke-argillite basement rock that forms the Ruahine and Tararua ranges. Plio-Pleistocene sediments overlie the greywacke-argillite, reflecting the presence of a shallow marine seaway that once linked the Ruataniwha Strait in the East Coast Basin to the Whanganui Basin (WB) (Fig. 16).

Cuts along the highway provide exposures through the sedimentary beds that can be seen dominantly dipping southwest, including the prominent Te Apiti Conglomerate (Rees et al. 2018b). The pebbles and cobbles in the conglomerate are dominated by greywacke, the same stone that makes up the main axial ranges of Aotearoa New Zealand. This suggests there was a source of greywacke somewhere to the northeast of the highway. Greywacke was being eroded and transported into a shallow marine environment by a river system to create a fan delta (Fig. 17). We see evidence for shallow marine conditions in the form of marine fossils that are found intermittently through the conglomerate beds.

The last appearance of *Crassostrea ingens* (giant oyster), *Maoricardium spatiosum*, *Polinicies waipipiensis* and *Phialopecten thomsoni* and the first appearance of *Zygochlamys delicatula* indicate deposition at ~2.4 Ma. This predates formation of the range, which is thought to have attained its current topographic expression over the last ~1 Ma, evidenced by a sudden influx of greywacke gravel into adjacent sedimentary basins (Fleming, 1953; Kingma, 1971, Townsend et al. 2008; Lee et al. 2011) and the presence of the ~1 Ma Kidnappers Ignimbrite in the Hawkes Bay, which must have been able to flow across the developing ranges at the time.

One of the characteristic features of this conglomerate is the steeply dipping foresets that reflect pebbles and cobbles being brought to the sea by the river before cascading down the front of the delta (Fig. 17). The river was constantly shifting through time in response to changes in energy, sediment supply, uplift and sea level. As a result, we see overlapping beds and erosional features within the conglomerate and a wide variety of sedimentary structures.

Figure 16: Paleogeography of the lower North Island at ~2.4 Ma. Sources of information include Beu (1995), King and Thrasher (1996), Field et al. (1997), King (2000), McIntyre (2002), Kamp et al. (2004), Pulford and Stern (2004), Bland (2006), Kamp and Furlong (2006), Bunce et al. (2009), Nicol (2011) and Trewick and Bland (2012).

Within this deposit, we find fragments of the scallop *Zygoclamys delicatula*. Today this scallop is mainly found in the cold waters off the lower South Island, but 2.4 million years ago this scallop made a brief appearance within the Manawātū Strait and adjacent marine basins. The migration of this cold-water scallop up into the North Island signals the start of the Quaternary Period when the first continental ice sheets began to form in the northern hemisphere. We saw specimens of this scallop at Stop 2 on Day 1, when visiting the Tuha Shellbed in the Rangitikei Valley.

Artesian groundwater was encountered within the conglomerate during construction of the road. This provided challenges during the construction of the piles for the Eco Viaduct across the wetland that occurs along the foot of the range.

As we travel to Palmerston North, we will cross the Manawātū Gorge, where the Manawātū River cuts east-west through an actively uplifting range. This is a good example of antecedent topography where the Manawātū River has maintained its course and eroded downwards as the Tararua and Ruahine ranges have been uplifted (Heerdegen & Shepherd 1992).

Figure 17: Schematic diagram showing the distribution of facies across the Gilbert-type fan delta (Rees et al. 2018a).

Return to Palmerston North

Stop 8 marks the end of our field trip around the WB. Field trip participants will be transported back to Palmerston North to be dropped off at the airport or accommodation. Please let the field trip leaders know where you want to be dropped off ahead of Stop 8. Safe travels and see you again in the Manawatū!

Figure 18: View east over the He Ara Kotahi pedestrian bridge and Manawatū River in Palmerston North (Central Economic Development Agency, 2022 - [ManawatuNZ.co.nz](https://www.manawatuNZ.co.nz)).

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Appendix A – Cyclothem Motifs

Whanganui cyclothem motifs, indicating paleogeographic position on the shelf and their position with respect to sea-level high and lowstands. Key surfaces, shell beds and systems tracts are shown (Saul et al. 1999; Pillans 2017).

Appendix B – Whanganui Basin Chronology

Figure from Naish et al. (1998).

Appendix C – Waitapu Shell Conglomerate Fossils

Fossils from the Waitapu Shell Conglomerate that represent a variety of subtidal to offshore environments: 1) *Alcithoe arabica*; 2) *Ostrea chilensis*; 3, 4) *Maoricrypta profunda*; 5) *Cominella adspersa*; 6, 7) *Purpurocardia purpurata*; 8) *Barbatia novaezelandiae*; 9, 10) *Austrovenus stutchburyi*; 11) *Alcithoe fusus*; 12) *Calliostoma punctulata*; 13) *Maoricolpus roseus*; 14) *Tanea zelandica*; 15) *Coelotrochus tiaratus*; 16) *Paphies delta*; 17) *Aeneator marshalli*; 18) *Pellicaria vermis*; 19, 23) *Cyclomactra tristis*; 20) *Paphies australis*; 21) *Barnea (Anchomasa) similis*; 22, 33) *Poireiria zelandica*; 24) *Chamaesipho columna*; 25) *Lima zelandica*; 26) *Austrofuscus glans*; 27) *Buccinulum vittatum*; 28) *Amalda novaezelandiae*; 29) *Amalda mucronata*; 30) *Haustrum scobina*; 31) *Cominella nassoides elegantula*; 32) *Cominella glandiformis*; 34) *Penion sulcatum*

Appendix D – Waitapu Shell Conglomerate Fossil List

Phylum	Class	Genus and species	Environment
Mollusca	Bivalvia	<i>Ostrea chilensis</i> Philippi (Küster, 1844)	Rocky intertidal
		<i>Barnea (Anchomasa) similis</i> (Gray, 1835)	
		<i>Barbatia novaezelandiae</i> (Smith, 1915)	
		<i>Austrovenus stutchburyi</i> (Wood, 1828)	Estuarine/lagoonal
		<i>Cyclomactra tristis</i> (Reeve, 1854)	
		<i>Paphies australis</i> (Gmelin, 1791)	
		<i>Paphies delta</i> Beu, 2006	Open coast/shoreface
		<i>Paphies donacina</i> (Spengler, 1793)	
		<i>Purpurocardia purpurata</i> (Deshayes, 1854)	
		<i>Lima zelandica</i> (Sowerby, 1877)	Soft-bottom shelf
	Gastropoda	<i>Calliostoma punctulatum</i> (Martyn, 1784)	Rocky intertidal
		<i>Coelotrochus tiaratus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1834)	
		<i>Buccinulum vittatum</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1833)	
		<i>Haustrum scobina</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1833)	
		<i>Paratrophon</i> sp.	
		<i>Cominella adspersa</i> (Bruguière, 1789)	Estuarine/lagoonal
		<i>Cominella glandiformis</i> (Reeve, 1846)	
		<i>Maoricolpus roseus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1834)	Open coast/shoreface
		<i>Maoricrypta profunda</i> (Hutton, 1873)	
		<i>Tanea zelandica</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1832)	
		<i>Pellicaria vermis</i> (Martyn, 1784)	
		<i>Cominella nassoides elegantula</i> (Finlay, 1926)	Soft-bottom shallow water to shelf
		<i>Alcithoe arabica</i> (Gmelin, 1791)	
<i>Penion sulcatum</i> (Lamarck, 1816)			
<i>Alcithoe fusus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1833)		Soft-bottom shelf	
<i>Aeneator marshalli</i> (Murdoch, 1924)			
<i>Austrofuscus glans</i> (Röding, 1798)			
<i>Amalda novaezelandiae</i> (Sowerby, 1859)			
<i>Amalda mucronata</i> (Sowerby, 1830)			
<i>Poirieria zelandica</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1833)			
Arthropoda		<i>Chamaesipho columna</i> (Spengler, 1790)	Rocky intertidal